

A STUDY ON THE IMPACT OF USERS' PREFERENCE BETWEEN FACEBOOK AND INSTAGRAM

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Abstract: *The purpose of the research is to make review of users' preference between Facebook and Instagram. Social media networks compete with each other, and they make an effort to increase their number of users which at the same time trying to create engagement. The main objective of this study to analyze the purpose of using the selected social media. There are two social media sites in the study area that are Facebook and Instagram. The study used 50 respondents for the purpose to get Facebook on social media sites like Facebook and Instagram and analyses the purpose of using most Facebook and Instagram and how does it work. Identify the difficulties faced by users of social media it is safe or not, social media is helpful to any business development.*

Key words: social media, Facebook, Instagram, image features, Users

Introduction

Today, social media have been increasing used to connect with one another. Consumer news content and share information. In the United States above 70% of the public have used social media. Facebook and Instagram are among the hottest social media platforms across the global, with 2.32 billion monthly active users respectively. Facebook and Instagram is the best strategy for markets to effectively reach their audience let's take a look at the data to determine whether Facebook or Instagram or Both. The study used 50 respondents for the purpose to get feedback on social media sites. The main objective of this research study is analyze the purpose of using the selected social media and how it benefits to the audience, what are difficulties faced by the audience in selected social media. Social media dominance has increased dramatically over the past few years with popular social networking sites like Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, Snapchat, etc. leading the race. Social media usage has witnessed an unprecedented growth over the past decade, thanks to Facebook and Instagram which dominate

the social media ecosystem. Social media has seen a significant surge in active monthly users in the last two years and looking at the numbers, it's only increasing with no signs of going back, it's almost surprising to see how social media has evolved over the past decade. Today, social media dominance has reached such an extent even the remotest parts of the world have knew about Facebook and Instagram, and they are most likely using it every day. Facebook undoubtedly dominates the social media scene in terms of audience reach and engagement, but Instagram is good at making noise too. This article looks at the two popular social media sites and explains how they differ from each other.

The following are the objective of the study

1. To Analyses the purpose of using the selected social media.
2. To identify the difficulties faced by users.
3. To find the benefits of selected social media.

Methodology and tools

This study is a social media related research. Has been used convenient sampling method for this study. Sampling design means collecting the samples from respondent. Data has been collected from 50 respondents. People connect on Facebook and Instagram every day. Your small business ads can show up as people are exploring what they're interested in, so making a connection with your business is easy. You decide who sees your Facebook or Instagram ad. Narrow down your ad's audience by interests, gender or location and use ad targeting to find the people most likely to click.

Data Collection

The primary data were collected in Bangalore in the month of February 2022 by using the online forms filling by respondent. Data were collected by online forms that respondent fill the form by using google forms. Social media analytics is all about collecting data from social media platforms and leveraging that information to make better, more intentional decisions for your organization. Consulting your Facebook and Instagram analytics regularly helps you understand how to use these platforms as a part of your marketing strategy, so your organization can grow and thrive. More than 3.8 billion people across the world use social media platforms every day. It's crowded and it's competitive. Social media analytics are an invaluable resource in gauging customer's interests.

Review of Literature

Olivia G Stewart “The social media’s affordances in the classroom” First Published on October 12, Even though the use of social media in education is a now widely-studied topic, there still does not seem to be a consensus for what social media may afford students or how best to use them in the classroom. In this critical review of current literature, I discuss some of the most prominent qualitative studies that explore the use of social media in the classroom.

Rob Sanders “Instagram vs Facebook should you use one or both” Rob Sanders is a digital marketing veteran with over 20 years of experience. During that time, Rob has helped a wide range of companies utilize new and emerging technologies to increase sales and profitability. As founder of RSO Consulting, Rob has helps clients maximize their digital marketing efforts via SEO, SEM, SMO, and web Analytics.

Bumsoo Kim [2018] Facebook v/s Instagram: How perceived qualification and technological attributes are related to change in social media usage level of Facebook and Instagram. Passing time, browsing need for as well as technology attributes of Facebook and Instagram surveyed respondents who have both Facebook and Instagram accounts. Respondents who were more qualified with entertainment and need for recognition aspects and those who have positive attitudes towards Facebook recommendation algorithm features were more likely to report that they have increased use of the platform.

Saleem Alhabash Mengyan Ma [2017] A Tale of four platforms motivation and users of Facebook, Twitter, Instagram and Snapchat: The current research explores differences between Facebook, Instagram, Twitter and Snapchat in terms of intensity of use. With regard to use motivations Snapchat takes the lead in five of the nine motivations. Findings are discussed in relation to the U&G approach and uniqueness of different social media and social networking sites.

Area of Study

The area of Study is Bengaluru. Social media refers to a range of internet – based platforms, applications and technologies that allow people to socially engage with one another online. Some of the common examples of social media platforms are Instagram, Facebook, Twitter, Pinterest etc. Businesses use social media marketing as a tool to gain website traffic or attention by implementing marketing campaigns and because of its cost – effective features and ability to provide a greater customer. Most businesses are entering into social media marketing, making it a necessity for today’s business.

Findings

Purpose of using social media

Billions of people around the world use social media to share information and make connections. On a personal level, social media allows you to communicate with friends and family, learn new things, develop your interests, and be entertained. On a professional level, you can use social media to broaden your knowledge in a particular field and build your professional network by connecting with other professionals in your industry. At the company level, social media allows you to have a conversation with your audience, gain customer feedback, and elevate your brand.

Table 1: Usage of social networking sites

S. No	Usage of social networking sites	No. Of respondents	Percentage %
01	Yes	43	86%
02	No	07	14%
	Total	50	100%

From the above table we can interpret that the how many members using the social networking

sites. In the table shows the 86% of people using social networking sites and 14% of people are not using social networking sites.

Table 2: Social media sites people used most

S. No	Most usage of social media networking sites	No. Of respondents	Percentage %
01	Facebook	18	36%
02	Instagram	32	64%
	Total	50	100%

From the above table we can interpret that the how offer respondents are using social networking sites. In the above table shows the 36% of people are using Facebook, 64% of people are using Instagram, 2% of people using Twitter.

Table 3: People preferred more Instagram and Facebook only for

S. No	Preferred most Instagram and Facebook only for	No. Of respondents	Percentage %
01	Entertainment	10	20%
02	Time pass	13	26%
03	Current updates	01	22%
04	Reels and videos	16	32%
	Total	50	100%

From the above table we can interpret that the why the people preferred most Instagram and Facebook only. In the above table shows for entertainment purpose 20% of people using this social media sites, for time pass purpose 26% of people using Instagram and Facebook, for

current updates purpose 22% of people using, for reels and videos 32% of peoples are using most Instagram and Facebook only.

Table 4: Time based on people active on social media networking sites

S. No	Timings people active on social media sites	No. Of respondents	Percentage %
01	5-7 AM	06	12%
02	1-3 PM	04	08%
03	7-9 PM	24	48%
04	After 9 PM	16	32%
	Total	50	100%

From the above table we can interpret that the which timings the peoples are active on social networking sites. In above table we can see that the peoples are active in 5 to 7AM is 12%, peoples are active in 1 to 3PM is 8%, peoples are active in 7 to 9PM is 48%, and peoples are active in after 9PM is 32%.

Table 5: Information peoples share on social media networking sites

S. No	Information people share on social networking sites	No. Of respondents	Percentage %
01	Email address	22	44%
02	Your work place and designation	08	16%
03	Personal photos and numbers	11	22%
04	Political views	09	18%
	Total	50	100%

From the above table we can interpret that the what are all the information shared on social networking sites. In the above table shows the peoples are sharing email address in social media is 44%, peoples sharing their social media 16% of work place and designation information and peoples sharing personal photos and numbers in social media is 22%, and peoples sharing 18% of political views information.

Difficulties faced by users

According to media reports, India is expected to reach 627 million social media users by 2019. A report by Internet and Mobile Association of India [IAMAI] reportedly showed that India had 451 million monthly active users as of March 31, 2019. The deeper internet penetration in India has led to a visible increase in the use of social media management platform Hootsuite, YouTube is the most popular social media platform in India followed by Facebook, WhatsApp, and Instagram.

Table 6: Distribution of sample respondents according to Accuracy

S. No	Peoples accuracy on social media networking sites	No. Of respondents	Percentage %
01	Fake news and Fake accounts	20	40%
02	Fraud	20	40%
03	No privacy	10	10%
	Total	50	100%

From the above table we can interpret that the Facebook is bad for society compare to Instagram why, in the above table we can see that the users mentioned some things in their words 30% of Facebook is spread fake news and fake accounts, 30% of Facebook is fraud, 10% of Facebook is don't have the privacy, and 30% of Facebook have a security problems in the society.

Table 7: Issues regarding safety and security

S. No	Safety and Security	No. Of respondents	Percentage %
01	Viruses	20	40%
02	Harrassed	18	36%
03	Identify theft	12	24%
	Total	50	100%

From the above table we can interpret that the people faced any security issues on Facebook or Instagram. Here we can see in the table the viruses issues in Facebook and Instagram and 36%

of people are facing the Harassment issue in Facebook and Instagram and 24% of people facing the identity theft issue in the Facebook and Instagram.

Table 8: Social media affecting Personal and Professional life

S. No	Affecting personal and professional life	No. Of respondents	Percentage %
01	Yes	33	66%
02	No	17	34%
	Total	50	100%

From the above table we can interpret that the peoples personal and professional life ever effected due to social media. In the above the people saying the 66% is yes their effected the personal and professional life in the social media and 34% of people said no their not effected on the social media in their personal and professional life.

Table 9: Other Problems

S. No	Other problems	No. Of respondents	Percentage %
01	Problem responding to comment	20	40%
02	Switching between account	00	00
03	Promoting photos and other platforms	00	00
04	All the above	30	60%
	Total	50	100%

From the above table we can interpret that the peoples facing the difficulties in Instagram. Here the people concluded that the peoples facing the 40% of problem responding to comment and 0% of people facing the switching between accounts and again 0% of peoples are facing the promoting photos and other platforms and 60% of people are facing the some other problems in Instagram.

Table 10: Social media affecting the mental health

S. No	Affecting the mental health	No. Of respondents	Percentage %
01	Yes	34	68%
02	No	16	32%
		50	100%

From the above table we can interpret that the social media networking sites had effected on your mental health. Here we can see that the people are 68% is effected on their mental health because of social media and 32% of people said that not effected the social media their mental health.

Benefits of selected social media

Benefits of selected social media is your reach large audience, you have a direct connection with your audience and you get to know them better and you provide better customer and you gain valuable insight about your customer and you see how your audience perceives your business, you can create organic content, you have access to paid advertising services, you build your brand, you drive traffic to your website, you can evaluate your performance, you can join social media networks for free, you can create viral content, you can uncover valuable insights.

Table 11: Promote Business

S. No	Promoting Business	No. Of respondents	Percentage %
01	Facebook	15	30%
02	Instagram	35	70%
	Total	50	100%

From the above table we can interpret that the social media platform should you use to promote your business. Here we can see that in the Facebook 30% is use to promote the business in the social media platform, in Instagram 70% is use to promote the business in the social media platform.

Table 12: Importance of social media in marketing

S. No	Important of social media in Marketing	No. Of respondents	Percentage %
01	Extremely Important	14	28%
02	Very Important	15	30%
03	Not So Important	14	28%
04	Not at all Important	07	14%
	Total	50	100%

From the above table we can interpret that the Instagram and Facebook for your marketing is important or not. Here we can see that the people said 28% is Instagram and Facebook for your marketing is extremely important, and 30% of people said that the Instagram and Facebook for your marketing is very important, and 28% of people said that the Instagram and Facebook for your marketing is not so important, 14% of people said that the Instagram and Facebook for your marketing is not at all important.

Conclusion

Instagram is limited to videos / photo, video, link etc., Facebook also has better posting systems more feature better user interface better cross platform support also the biggest win is that Facebook has more users and has been around longer than Instagram. It is becoming more popular, but Facebook definitely has more users. All those who are on Instagram are definitely on Facebook too. In this article we took 50 responses in that all most audience of social media chosen Instagram and they most use Instagram now a days and they said Instagram provide or helpful to business promotion. I can see Facebook and Instagram being a winning combination. Marketers can reach both audiences where they spend their time, with content that is relevant and effective. If your brand's audience is more focused (older or younger), then it may be best served with one platform or the other. Lastly, if you still feel unsure, try out both platforms and do some testing. After all, the last thing you want to do is leave anything to chance. To learn more about other Digital marketing strategies and best practices, do check out our Digital Marketing Certificate Course and Post Graduate Program in Digital Marketing. For years, we have focused on building the best experience for sharing photos with your friends and family. Now, we will be able to work even more closely with the Instagram team to also offer the best experience for sharing beautiful mobile photos with people based on your interests. We believe these are different experiences that complement each other. But in order to do this well, we need to be mindful about keeping and building on Instagram's strengths and features rather than just trying to integrate everything into Facebook. That's why we are committed to building

and growing Instagram independently. Millions of people around the world love the Instagram app and the brand associated with it, and our goal is to help spread this app and brand to even more people.

References

1. Alhabash, S., Chiang, Y. H., Huang, K. [2014]. MAM & U&G in Taiwan: Differences in the uses and gratifications of Facebook as a function of motivational reactivity. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 35, 423-430.
2. Anderson, J. A., Meyer, T. P. [1975]. Functionalism and the mass media. *Journal of Broadcasting*, 19, 11-22.
3. Duggan, M. [2015a]. The demographics of social media users. Pew Research Center. Retrieved from <http://www.pewinternet.org/2015/08/19/the-demographics-of-social-media-users/>
4. Facebook. [2016]. Newsroom: Company info: Stats. Retrieved from <http://newsroom.fb.com/company-info/>
5. Instagram. [2016]. Our story: A quick walk through our history as a company. Retrieved from <http://www.instagram.com/press/?hl=en>